

Interference :

In the determination of 5 ppm of manganese at pH 9.1±0.1 the following ions do not interfere to the extents (µg/ml) given in the parentheses : CH₃COO⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, or B₄O₇²⁻ (500); PO₄³⁻ (100); Na⁺, K⁺, Li⁺, Rb⁺ or Cs⁺ (500); Ba²⁺ or Sr²⁺ (250); Ag⁺ (50); Cd²⁺ (20); MoO₄²⁻ or WO₄²⁻ (20). However, Cu²⁺, Pd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Fe³⁺, VO₃⁻, EDTA and fluoride seriously interfere at all concentrations. The use of common masking agents to eliminate their interferences was not fruitful.

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Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium and Uranium with 4-Methyl Daphnetin

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VANADIUM and uranium metals are frequently mined together. Although reliable analytical procedures for their determination are known, very little work has appeared on the simultaneous spectrophotometric analysis of these metals.

4-methyl daphnetin forms an orange-yellow complex with uranium (λ_{max} 450 nm) and a bluish-green complex with vanadium (λ_{max} 600 nm) in the pH range 5 and 7. The present work reports a simple and quick simultaneous spectrophotometric method of analysis of vanadium and uranium with 4-methyl daphnetin.

From the spectrophotometric properties of the complexes.

Complex	λ _{max} nm	ε ₄₅₀	ε ₆₀₀	Sandell sensitivity µg/cm ²
V(v)-4-methyl daphnetin	600	6375	900	0.006
U(vi)-4-methyl daphnetin	450	2700	0	0.030

The relationships (1) and (2)

$$A_{450} = \epsilon_{450}^V [V] + \epsilon_{450}^U [U] \quad (1)$$

$$A_{600} = \epsilon_{600}^V [V] + \epsilon_{600}^U [U] \quad (2)$$

were used to develop the following equations :

$$[V] \times 10^4 = 1.266 A_{600}$$

$$[U] \times 10^4 = 3.7 A_{450} - 3.4 A_{600}$$

Several synthetic mixtures were prepared and analysed satisfactorily.

Procedure

To an aliquot containing 0.8 to 1.6 µg of V (v) and 10-25 µg of UO₂²⁺ is added 4 ml of 0.1M alcoholic solution of 4-methyl daphnetin. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 5 and 7 and the resulting solution diluted to 25 ml. The absorbance of the solutions are measured at 450 and 600 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. The amounts of metals are computed from the appropriate simultaneous equations. A large number of anions do not interfere in the estimation, however Mo, Fe, Ti, W interfere and should be eliminated.

Structures of the Reaction Products from Reaction of Resorcinol with N-Benzoyl Phthalimide

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AN organic dye has been synthesised by the condensation of Resorcinol with N-Benzoyl phthalimide which is a known compound. It behaves like florescene, a dye.

Experimental

Three gms. of phthalimide was benzoylated by the usual procedure¹. The crude N-benzoyl phthalimide was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 115°, yield 0.8 gm.

Found : C=71.8, H=3.8, N=5.3% Molecular weight by Rast=248. Calculated for $C_{15}H_9O_3N$, C=72.1, H=3.57, N=5.5% Molecular weight 251.

Condensation of Resorcinol with N-benzoyl phthalimide² :

Three gms. of the benzoyl derivative was condensed with 6 gms. of resorcinol in presence of conc. H_2SO_4 on a sand bath till it attained a reddish brown colour. It was diluted with water neutralised with 200 gms. of $BaCO_3$ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated on a water bath. The residue was dried in vacuum dessicator.

Purification :

The mass was completely dried in a drying pistol and the dried mass was treated with absolute alcohol. Some portion of the dried mass was dissolved in alcohol. The alcohol was distilled and the residue was dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a vacuum dessicator. This dried mass when subjected to TLC gave two distinct spots showing it to be a mixture of two components.

Separation of two components from its mixture :

The dried mass was treated with acetone when a small amount of the dried mass dissolved leaving behind a residue.

(a) The acetone soluble component :

The acetone was distilled and the concentrated syrupy mass was crystallised after cooling in an ice bath into a reddish brown amorphous powder, yield 1.20 gms. It gave a greenish violet fluorescence in dil. NaOH. solution.

(b) The acetone insoluble component :

It was dried by evaporating the adhered acetone and then crystallised from absolute alcohol into dark brownish amorphous powder yield 1.6 gms. It also gave a dull green violet fluorescence in dil. NaOH.

From the above experiments, it was concluded that during condensation N-benzoyl phthalimide which has three carbonyl groups i.e. (A, B & C) might react with resorcinol so that the carbonyl group (A) reacts giving different products (1) and (2) as given in Figure.

NOTES

Both these compounds gave a violet blue coloration with $FeCl_3$ showing the presence of phenolic groups. Being isomeric the compound 1 & 2 gave the micro analysis result which are as follows :

Compound No. 1

Found C=72.3, H=4.2, N=3.4% Mol. wt. by Rast 432 Calculated for $C_{27}H_{17}O_5N$, C=72.1, H=3.9, N=3.2% Mol. wt. 435.

Compound No. 2

Found C=72.18, H=4.16, N=3.4% Mol. wt. by Rast 434 Calculated for $C_{27}H_{17}O_5N$, C=72.1, H=3.9, N=3.2% Mol. wt. 435

Further the confirmation of two different isomers was done on the basis of their IR spectra³.

IR spectra of compound (1)

700 cm^{-1} , 1075 cm^{-1} Mono substitution in benzene ring, 1085 cm^{-1} 1126 cm^{-1} o-disubstituted benzene ring (strong) 750 cm^{-1} 1, 2, 3 Trisubstituted benzene ring, 1580 cm^{-1} carbonyl groups attached to benzene ring, 1620 cm^{-1} for phenyl group and 1200 cm^{-1} , 1410 cm^{-1} , 3600 cm^{-1} , for phenolic OH group. 1270 cm^{-1} for aromatic ether linkage.

IR spectra of compound (2)

700 cm^{-1} , 1075 cm^{-1} mono substitution, in benzene ring, 1085 cm^{-1} , 1126 cm^{-1} o-disubstitution, 1170 cm^{-1} 1,2,4 trisubstituted benzene ring, 1580 cm^{-1} carbonyl groups attached to benzene ring; 1620 cm^{-1} for phenyl group and 1200 cm^{-1} , 1410 cm^{-1} , 3600 cm^{-1} for phenolic OH group, 1270 cm^{-1} for aromatic ether linkage.

The main difference between the two spectras were in the peaks at 750 cm^{-1} for 1, 2, 3 trisubstituted and 1170 cm^{-1} for 1, 2, 4 trisubstituted benzene rings in structure (1) and (2) respectively.

On the basis of above difference in the peaks the compound No. 1 gives dull coloured fluorescence

due to the presence of shorter conjugated chain for resonance while the compound No. 2 shows deep coloured fluorescence due to the presence of long conjugated chain for resonance (according to E. R. Watson theory of color).

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Phytochemical Studies on *Salvia coccinea* Linn

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In view of the high medicinal importance and utility of *Salvia species*¹ (Family-Labiata) in various ailments such as diarrhoea, haemorrhoids, lung diseases, gangrene etc., a systematic chemical investigation of *Salvia coccinea*² Linn. on which no phytochemical work seems to have been done so far, has been undertaken in this laboratory. It is a slender herb, 1-2 ft. high; native of S. America. It also grows between 3500-7000 ft. in the West Himalayas.

The air dried powdered whole plant of *S. coccinea* (1.5 Kg.) was extracted successively with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and benzene.

Petroleum ether concentrate was subjected to chromatography over Brockmann alumina. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) mixture yielded a compound (0.02 gm.) which on crystallisation from acetone gave a colourless solid m.p. 84°-85°. The I. R. spectrum of the solid discloses its alcoholic nature (ν_{\max} . 3300 cm^{-1} associated-OH). The mass spectrum of the compound in addition to molecular ion peak at m/e 452, exhibits ion peaks at m/e 434 (M-18) and m/e 31 (-CH₂OH). The physical properties of the compound were found to be very similar to those reported for n-hentriacontanol³ which was finally confirmed by the direct comparison (m.m.p., Co.T.L.C. & CO.I.R.) with an authentic sample of n-hentriacontanol.

Elution with benzene afforded a product (0.15 gm.) which on crystallisation from methanol gave shining white flakes, m.p. 134°-136°. It showed bluish-violet colouration with Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol (ν_{\max} . 3560 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl and 1649 cm^{-1} for unsaturation). The mass spectrum of the compound recorded fragment ion peaks at m/e 396 (M-18), 273 (M-side chain, C₁₀H₂₁) and m/e 255 [(M-18)-side chain. i. e., C₁₀H₂₁], besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 414. It forms an acetate m.p. 128° and a benzoate, m.p. 142°. The identity of the compound as β -sitosterol has been established by m.m.p. determination, Co-T.L.C. and CO.I.R. with the authentic specimen of the compound.

Further elution with benzene furnished a very small quantity (0.005 gm.) of another crystalline solid, m.p. 210°-212°, which responds to positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for triterpene. Further characterisation of the compound was not possible due to paucity of the material.

The benzene extract on chromatography over Brockmann alumina in the usual way afforded only β -sitosterol in the benzene chloroform (1:1) eluate.

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Chemical Constituents of *Rumex orientalis* Bernh

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RUMEX orientalis Bernh. syn. *Rumex patinitia* Linn, a native of Europe, is found in Western Himalayas from Kumaon to Kashmir. Its roots are reported to be used as purgative¹, and are known to contain some anthraquinone derivatives². A survey.